

Original Research

Human Resource for Health Job Satisfaction: Working Conditions in Public Healthcare in Tanzania's Local Government Authorities

Richard Msacky¹

¹Department of Business Administration, College of Business Education, P.O
Box 2077, Dodoma, Tanzania

Sophia Assey

²Department of Human Resource Management, Local Government Training
Institute, P.O Box 1125, Dodoma, Tanzania

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Abstract

The study is centered on the influence of working conditions on job satisfaction in public healthcare facilities and human resources for health in local government authorities (LGAs) in Dodoma City, Tanzania. This study is built on Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory and references from theoretical and empirical literature. A quantitative approach was adopted during data collection and analysis. A cross-sectional design was employed to collect data from 230 human resources for health in Dodoma City using a questionnaire. Descriptive and inferential statistics were employed in the data analysis. Descriptive statistics is used to present the respondents' demographic information and job satisfaction level in the LGA of Dodoma City. Likewise, the influence of working conditions on job satisfaction is predicted using a binary logistic regression model. The findings revealed that most human resources for health in the LGAs have a high experience of job dissatisfaction. Similarly, it was revealed that working tools, the working environment, working hours, work schedules, policy, and administration are significantly associated with job satisfaction among human resources for health in LGAs in Dodoma City. Likewise, the study's findings noted that human resources for health working under improved conditions in LGAs experience high job satisfaction compared to those working under unimproved conditions. The findings suggest that the government should consistently improve working conditions to guarantee human resources for health and high levels of job satisfaction in public healthcare facilities.

Keywords: Dodoma City, human resource for health, Job satisfaction, Local Government Authorities, working conditions.

¹ Corresponding author's Email: rimsaki@yahoo.com

Introduction

Employees' positive and negative feelings and attitudes about their work are referred to as job satisfaction (Armstrong, 2020). Positive feelings and attitudes are associated with job satisfaction, while negative feelings and attitudes of employees indicate employee dissatisfaction. Increased staff involvement in the organisation's performance, lower labour turnover rates, and higher service quality are all benefits of increased job satisfaction (Kvist et al., 2014). Dissatisfied employees are more likely to leave the organisation, leaving the remaining staff members with a heavy workload. Additionally, unhappy workers may become demotivated, leading to low performance and services within the organisation (Ngasengayire & Ngatuni, 2021). Job satisfaction is essential to delivering improved quality services in the health sector because the satisfaction level of an individual in his chosen career determines his commitment to his/her responsibility. Higher job satisfaction results in better employee and patient satisfaction (Lasebikan et al., 2020). Job satisfaction is associated with various factors, including supervision skills, the job itself, working conditions, growth, advancement, status, job security, relationship with others, career development opportunities, challenging job and teamwork, and motivational incentives (Macias & Bustillo, 2014; Armstrong, 2020).

The research indicates that working conditions significantly impact job satisfaction (Geta, et al., 2021; Dalkrani & Dimitriadis, 2018; ILO, 2013). Studies based on the working conditions as a factor of job satisfaction indicate that employees desire to work in a safe and pleasant environment. Robbins (1998) adds that employees prefer working conditions similar to those in their homes. Evidence from Austria discovered that a relationship with the supervisor holds the most significance to job satisfaction, followed by professional development opportunities, satisfaction with working hours, infrastructure, working conditions, and salary (Grisseemann, et al., 2020). Moreover, a study conducted in Sweden by Toropova et al. (2020) regarding school working conditions and job satisfaction among teachers revealed a strong relationship between working conditions and job satisfaction.

According to a study in Ethiopia, the three main factors affecting job satisfaction among human resources for health in Africa are a bad working environment, a heavy workload, and long work hours (Kim, et al., 2021). Thus, policymakers and health managers need to pay special attention to the benefits packages and working conditions of human resources for health at different levels (Merga & Fufa, 2019). Similarly, a study by Akinwale and George (2020) regarding work environment and job satisfaction among nurses in government tertiary hospitals in Nigeria revealed that specific aspects of working conditions, such as administrative and managerial support, autonomous work and supervision from superiors, directly influence job satisfaction.

In Tanzania, human resources for health working in Local Government Authorities (LGAs) are managed through a decentralised health system of arrangement, introduced through decentralisation by devolution in the 1990s (Kessy, 2018). Decentralisation by devolution gave the LGAs the mandate to create autonomous and democratic institutions to provide quality service to the people, including health care. Similarly, in the 1990s, Tanzania embarked on Health Sector Reform (HSR) to enhance quality health service

delivery and increase human resources for health job satisfaction and working conditions (Munjinja & Kida, 2014). Under decentralisation by devolution and HSR, LGAs were empowered to plan, provide and monitor health service delivery in the healthcare facilities (district hospitals, health centres, and dispensaries) (Marijani, 2017). Likewise, LGAs were mandated to recruit and retain human resources for health and allocate and budget for human resources in LGAs (Siril & Simba, 2021; Kisumbe & Mashala, 2020).

The health sector is one of the unsafe work environments for human resources as it is surrounded by risks while practising and enjoying the right to health for all; thus, human resources for health should have safe working conditions (WHO, 2020). According to ILO (2013), working conditions encompass working time, working tools, rest periods, policies, and physical and mental demands. Healthy and safe working conditions in the health sector prevent avoidable harm to patients and human resources for health and improve the quality of care and job satisfaction (WHO, 2022; ILO, 2013). Hence, human resources for health need to work under proper working conditions to increase job satisfaction, leading to good job performance. Studies in low and middle-income countries, including Tanzania, noted that human resources for health in public health facilities face challenges related to poor working conditions, lack of equipment, poor motivation, shortage of supplies, lack of electricity, poor safety and infrastructure (Bolan et al., 2021; Shemdoo et al., 2016). Thus, the persistent challenges prompt human health resources to flee their expertise to the private health sector and non-governmental organisations (Siril & Simba, 2021; Bolan, et al., 2021). In the same vein, the report by the Controller and Auditor General (CAG) emphasised that health facilities under LGAs in Tanzania, including Dodoma, have a high scarcity of medical equipment and working tools (United Republic of Tanzania (URT), 2024).

To improve the working conditions, Tanzania, through the Ministry of Health, Community Development, Gender, Elderly and Children (MHCDGEC), requested support from the WHO in developing and implementing a national programme for occupational health and safety programme for human resources for health, which started in 2016 (WHO, 2023). Also, Tanzania enacted law No. 5 of health safety in the workplace in 2003 under the administration of the Occupational Safety and Health Agency (OSHA), established in 1997 as part of the public sector reforms. Likewise, in 2019, Tanzania, under the umbrella of OSHA, distributed guidelines in the healthcare facilities on working conditions for human resource health to 9 regions, including Dodoma (WHO, 2023). Moreover, in 2017, Tanzania released a new health sector policy that emphasised quality and universal health coverage through improved working conditions of human resources for health (URT, 2017). Despite the efforts taken by the government, the report by the Controller and Auditor General (CAG) revealed that the health sector under LGAs in Tanzania has challenges related to the scarcity of working tools, lack of enough health workers, heavy workload, limited budget, and lack of infrastructure (URT, 2022). The persistence of this state of affairs may affect employee's job satisfaction.

Research on job satisfaction has yielded inconsistent findings. For example, the study by Kisumbe and Mashala (2020) revealed that public health employees in Tanzania are satisfied with their jobs at 68%, while the study by Msanya (2020) concluded that human resources for health in Tanzania are dissatisfied with their jobs at 51%. Thus, there are mixed findings regarding job satisfaction among human health resources. Similarly,

several other studies conducted had their focus on different sectors, specifically studies conducted by Toropova et al. (2020); Zafarullah and Pertti (2019), Abdu and Nzilano (2018) focused on job satisfaction among teachers from the education sector. Likewise, studies conducted by Ngasengayire and Ngatuni (2021), Mongi (2020), Nurvitasari (2019), and Dalkrani and Dimitriadis (2018) on job satisfaction had their focus on employees generally without focusing human resources of specific sectors like health. Also, studies by Jumanne et al. (2021) and Rahman et al. (2017) dealt with job satisfaction among workers in the banking and insurance sectors, respectively.

Moreover, other studies from Tanzania context dealt with working conditions and job performance (Myeya & Rupia, 2022; Swai & Tieng'o, 2022). Thus, studies on working conditions and job satisfaction of human resources for health in Local Government Authorities in Tanzania are still scant. The survey on working conditions among human resources of a specific sector like health is important to provide insights on building employees' morale and enhancing their retention in the LGAs such as Dodoma City Council in Tanzania. Also, a study on working conditions and job satisfaction is salient for benchmarking Tanzania's human resources for health conditions against international standards. Similarly, this study is essential in providing valuable evidence-based data to policy and decision-makers, especially in the LGAs, for improving working conditions and job satisfaction. Therefore, this study is set to assess the influence of working conditions on job satisfaction in public healthcare facilities among human resources for health in LGAs, drawing on experience from Dodoma City, Tanzania.

Theoretical review

Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory served as a foundation for this research. The theory was developed by Fredrick Herzberg in 1957. This theory has developed a hypothesis to describe the cause of job satisfaction and dissatisfaction among individuals. According to the theory, employee satisfaction can be gauged using the motivating and hygiene factors (Gupta, 2022). The motivating or satisfier factors include job achievement, personal growth, responsibility, and opportunities for advancement. An increase in these factors will lead to satisfaction, but a decrease in these factors leads to employee dissatisfaction (Armstrong, 2020), including human resources for health. Hygiene factors related to the environment in which employees operate don't provide satisfaction, but their nonexistence results in dissatisfaction. The hygiene factors include company policy and administration, supervision, relationship with peers, supervisors and subordinates, salary, job security, working conditions, and status (Dartey-Baah & Amoako, 2011).

Among the hygiene factors under this theory, working conditions were studied to indicate their influence on job satisfaction among human resources for health in LGAs in Dodoma City. It reflects the physical conditions of the work environment and whether there are good or bad working tools available at the workplace (Saat et al., 2021). This theory has guided understanding of the subject under study, identifying the problem, answering study questions, and discussing the results. A survey by Malik and Neema (2013) revealed that recognition, nature of work, supervision, and working conditions are significantly associated with job satisfaction. Job dissatisfaction among employees working in Oman hospitals was related to inadequate salary, heavy workload, recognition, and poor organisational policies (Alrawah et al., 2020). In Pakistani, hygiene factors were

discovered to have a strong influence on job satisfaction among staff working in insurance companies (Rahman et al., 2017). Nevertheless, this theory faces criticisms from other scholars for its failure to identify external factors associated with job satisfaction. Furthermore, people are different and they are satisfied differently. It is unnecessary for satisfying factors identified in this theory to satisfy all people because a hygiene factor to one person may be a motivational factor to another (Gupta, 2022). Despite its critique, the theory has been used by different scholars in their studies (Kisumbe & Mashala, 2020; Alrawah et al., 2020; Rahman et al., 2017; Malik & Neema, 2013). Thus, this theory is relevant as it provides indicators for assessing employees' satisfaction with the local government authorities in Tanzania, specifically regarding human resources for health.

Research methods and materials

The study was conducted at Dodoma City Council. Dodoma City was purposively selected among the seven councils of the Dodoma Region in Tanzania. The City has recently experienced an increased population due to the shifting of government offices in 2016 from Dar es Salaam City to Dodoma City (URT, 2022; Msacky, et al., 2017). The 2022 Population and Housing Census reported Dodoma City Council with the largest population of 765,179 compared to other councils, namely Kondoa District (244,854), Kondoa Town (80,443), Mpwapwa District (403,247), Kongwa District (443,867), Chamwino District (486,176), Bahi District (322,526) and Chemba District (339,333). Dodoma City statistics indicated an increase of 354,223 populations compared to the 2012 Population and Housing Census, which showed the Dodoma City population to be 210,956. The growth in population puts more pressure on service delivery, including devising a job satisfaction strategy for retaining the human resources for health under the LGAs. The report (URM, 2017) stresses that population growth will lead to more healthcare professionals, hospitals, and health centres to accommodate the increasing population. Also, an increase in population has a direct proportion to the workload of health workers who will have to serve a large number of people, impacting job satisfaction. Similarly, among LGAs in Tanzania, Dodoma City has health challenges, including a shortage of human resources for health (Msacky, 2024).

A cross-sectional design was adopted in this study to collect data from human resources for health workers in LGAs in Dodoma City. The total population of the study was 541, and the Yamane formula (1967), expressed in equation (1), was applied to compute the sample size to 230.

$$n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2} \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

Where n= sample size

N= Population size

e =level of precision.

$$n = \frac{541}{1+541(0.05)^2} = 229.96 \approx 230$$

A stratified sampling technique was used to select human resources for health working in the LGAs in Dodoma City. The strata were organised based on the health service structure operating in the LGAs after the HSR of the 1990s. According to the HSR, the health service delivery in the LGAs has three levels: dispensary, health centre, and district hospital. Thus, in each level of health service delivery, a significant number of human resources for health. In this study, each level of health service delivery is regarded as a stratum from which a proportionate sample is obtained. Then, a table of random numbers was used to pick the respondents from the list of human resources working in a particular level of health service delivery. Table 1 indicates how a sample size was drawn from each stratum. A sample of 230 obtained was consistent with Mugenda & Mugenda's (2003) suggestion that a sample size for statistical analysis larger than 30 and less than 500 should be adequate. This technique was also used in the study by Mwititi et al. (2021) and proved efficient.

Table 1. Population strata and sample size

Health facility	Number of employees	Proportion	Sample size
St Gemma Hospital	165	$165/541 \times 230$	70
Health Centers	315	$315/541 \times 230$	134
Dispensaries	61	$61/541 \times 230$	26
TOTAL	541	$541/541 \times 230$	230

Source: CHMT report (2022)

Similarly, a five-point Likert scale questionnaire was used to collect quantitative data from 230 respondents. The first part of the questionnaire was meant to capture demographic characteristics of age, location, occupation, sex, age, and education; the second part captured the working conditions and job satisfaction aspects of human resources for health. The job satisfaction assessment had seven items, including salary, recognition, achievement, supervision, job security and opportunity for growth and job content, which were measured using a 5-point Likert scale where 1-strongly dissatisfied, 2-dissatisfied, 3-neither dissatisfied nor satisfied, 4- satisfied, 5- strongly satisfied. The seven aspects were adopted and modified from previous studies (Geta et al., 2021; Msanya, 2020; Lu et al., 2016; Ghayas & Siddiqui, 2012; Spector, 1997). Similarly, the working conditions assessment had five items, which are working tools, working environment, working hours, work schedules, and policy and administration measured using a 5-point Likert scale where 1-strongly disagree, 2-disagree, 3-neither disagree nor agree, 4- agree, 5- strongly agree. All 230 copies of the questionnaire were returned due to various efforts employed, which included selecting other respondents from the list in the healthcare facility to cover the absent respondents during the survey. Also, the questionnaire was read to respondents in *Kiswahili's* national language so they could understand the questions asked properly before answering them.

The reliability of the data was measured by Cronbach alpha, presented in Table 2. Cronbach's alpha coefficient values range from 0 to 1, which is used to rate internal consistency. The rationale for internal consistency is that the individual items should all be measuring the same constructs and thus correlate positively with one another (Creswell, 2014). The value of Cronbach's alpha has a different degree of acceptability. The Cronbach's alpha value of 0.90 or above is considered good or excellent. An alpha

between 0.80 and 0.89 is considered good, while 0.70 and 0.79 is considered adequate or acceptable. Alpha between 0.60 and 0.69 is considered questionable, 0.50 and 0.60 are considered poor, and values less than 0.50 are considered acceptable (Pallant, 2007). Thus, the findings in Table 2 show that all factors had an alpha value above the permissible level of 0.70, as recommended by Pallant (2007).

Table 2. Overall Reliability Statistics

Variables	Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
Working Condition	0.733	5
Job satisfaction	0.725	7
Overall	0.729	12

The data were quantitatively analysed with the help of the computer software Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). The quantitative methods applied were descriptive and inferential statistics to assess the influence of working conditions on job satisfaction among human resources for health in Local Government Authorities in Dodoma City. Descriptive statistics in frequency, mean, and standard deviation were used to explain the demographic information of the human resources department for health and the respondents' job satisfaction level. Similarly, descriptive statistics was applied to transform the five Likert scale responses from the human resource for health into an index scale using the overall mean scores of working conditions and job satisfaction. Then, the overall mean was used to categories the responses into groups of improved working conditions, unimproved working conditions for the independent variable, and satisfied and dissatisfied for the dependent variable. Thus, in this analysis, the mean score from the mean and above was regarded as the category of human resources with improved working conditions. Also, the mean score below the overall mean was considered a category of human resource for health with unimproved working conditions experience. Likewise, the overall mean score criteria were used to categorise job satisfaction into two groups of human resources for health. The first category refers to human resources, whose mean score is gauged from the mean score and above. This first category was referred to as human resource for health with job satisfaction. The second category represents human resources for health, whose mean scores were below the overall mean. This second category was referred to as human resource for health with dissatisfaction on the job. Previous studies (Msacky, 2024; Chilipweli et al., 2023; Geta et al., 2021; Lu et al., 2016) adopted the overall mean approach to transform the five Likert scale into binary responses for further statistical analysis.

Similarly, the data pattern was examined using the Chi-square before the individual variables were added to the binary logistic regression model. The bivariate analysis for the Chi-square test was conducted, considering that all the independent variables with a P-value of less than 0.05 were regarded as significantly associated with job satisfaction. The variables tested using a Chi-square against the outcome variable were the type of health facility, occupation/cadre, sex, age, education, and working condition

Then, inferential statistics employed the Binary Logistic Regression Model (BLRM) to predict the influence of working conditions on job satisfaction of human resources for health. The model's findings are presented as a regression using the odds ratio (OR). The

estimated OR was determined by taking the exponent of the regression parameter estimates. The OR shows the increase or decrease in the likelihood that human resources for health would attain job satisfaction at a given level of the independent variable compared to those in the reference category (Hosmer & Lemeshow, 2000). Also, it is important to note that before performing the BLRM, the 5-point Likert scale data on job satisfaction among human resources for health were transformed into an index scale using the overall mean scores. Using the overall mean score, job satisfaction with a score greater or equal to the overall mean was labelled as 0 = satisfied human resource for health and 1= dissatisfied human resource health with a score below the overall mean. Thus, the BLRM was expressed using equation (2) as follows:

$$\log it[\pi(x)] = \log \left(\frac{\pi(x)}{1-\pi(x)} \right) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x_1 + \dots + \beta_p x_p \quad (2)$$

Where $\pi(x)$ the likelihood of job satisfaction is, a set of independent variables represents the coefficient of a respective independent variable. The findings from the model were presented in a regression in the form of an Unadjusted Odds Ratio (UOR) and Adjusted Odds Ratio (AOR). The term UOR refers to the influence of independent predictors, such as working tools, on the outcome variable (job satisfaction without other variables). The Adjusted Odds Ratio refers to the association of a specific variable, an outcome variable, with the presence of other variables (controlling all other variables). Thus, Unadjusted Odds Ratio (UOR) and Adjusted Odds Ratio regression analyses were conducted. Agresti (2002) recommended that all predictors that exhibited a p-value of less than 0.2 in the unadjusted regression should be included in the model for adjusted analysis.

Results and discussion

The findings and discussions about job satisfaction and working conditions are presented in this section. Descriptive and inferential statistics were used to generate the results. This section's primary components are the demographic characteristics of the respondents, associations between working conditions and job satisfaction, and the influence of working conditions on job satisfaction. These are the main parts that constitute this section.

Demographic characteristics of respondents

Table 3 shows that the study involved 230 participants, out of which 156 were female and 74 were male. This domination exists worldwide as women comprise 70% of the entire health workforce. It is reported that many people rely more on women for healthcare services than men (Schwartz, 2022). A majority of the participants were from health centres, 134 (58.26%), followed by the district hospital (30.43%). Respondents were from different health cadres, including nurses 59 (25.65%), clinical officers 37 (16.09%), laboratory technicians 31 (13.48%), medical doctors 14 (6.09%), medical attendants 22 (9.57%) and others 32 (13.91%). The category of others comes from non-

medical human resources supporting health service delivery. The non-medical human resources include drivers, security guards, accountants, and secretaries. Thus, the number of non-medical human resources was expected to be small compared to those with medical backgrounds, such as nurses, clinicians, laboratory technicians, and medical doctors. Also, Table 3 indicates that respondents aged 20-35 (64.35%) dominated the study, followed by those aged 36-50 (32.17%). The findings show that most of the respondents are in their active years of work and are in more need of achieving job satisfaction than the older group. Concerning education qualification, respondents with university/college education were majority 218 (94.78%). Education level was important as it showed respondents had received formal education, allowing them to understand the study and fill in the distributed questionnaire. The results are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Social demographic characteristics of respondents

Variable	Frequency	Percent
Sex		
Male	74	32.17
Female	156	67.83
Location		
District Hospital	70	30.43
Health Center	134	58.26
Dispensary	26	11.30
Occupation		
Medical Doctor	14	6.09
Clinical officer	37	16.09
Nurse	59	25.65
Pharmacist	19	8.26
Medical attendant	22	9.57
Laboratory technician	31	13.48
Health officer	16	6.96
Others	32	13.91
Age of respondent		
20-35	148	64.35
36-50	74	32.17
51 and above	8	3.48
Education qualification		
Secondary	11	4.78
University/college	218	94.78
Other	1	0.43

Respondents' perceptions of job satisfaction

This part tried to capture respondents' perceptions of job satisfaction. The descriptive analysis was run to identify employees' job satisfaction based on seven main criteria: salary, recognition, achievement, supervision, job security, growth opportunities, and job content. Job satisfaction level among human resources for health in Local Government Authorities at Dodoma City was computed using mean, frequency, and percentage scores.

This approach was adopted in previous studies (Msacky, 2024; Chilipweli et al., 2023; Geta et al., 2021; Lu et al., 2016). The findings in Table 4 show that the overall mean score for job satisfaction was 2.90. Using the overall mean criteria, the mean score for salary (2.72), recognition for contribution (2.83), achievement (2.81), supervision (2.88), and job content (2.77) were below the overall mean score. Similarly, the findings revealed that job security (2.90) and opportunity for growth (3.24) were above the overall mean score. The implication of the findings is that employees' overall job satisfaction was low because most of the measured items scored below the overall mean score. As calculated in Table 4, the overall mean score was 2.90; thus, respondents below the mean score were grouped in the dissatisfied category.

The findings of the mean score are in tandem with a study by Msanya (2020) which revealed that human resources for health are most dissatisfied with the income/benefit package at Kilimanjaro Christian Medical Centre Referral Hospital in Tanzania. The study by Grisseemann et al. (2020) revealed that employees in the Alpine Hospitality Industry are mostly dissatisfied with their salaries. Job satisfaction was greatly related to opportunities for development, working conditions, and relationships with supervisors. Similarly, Alrawah et al., (2020) revealed that people are dissatisfied with their work due to a lack of recognition. The findings call for the attention of the government and all responsible organs to ensure that the job satisfaction level of the employees is improved by developing strategies and opportunities in the LGAs.

Table 4. Job satisfaction level of respondents

Indicators	Mean±Std
Fair salary for the work	2.72±1.23
Recognition for the contribution	2.83±1.18
Achievement	2.81±1.27
Supervision and guidance	2.88±1.22
Jo security	2.90±1.25
Opportunity for growth	3.24±1.42
Job content	2.77±1.29
OVERALL	2.90±0.81

In the next level of analysis, the study used the overall mean score of job satisfaction to establish two categories (dissatisfied and satisfied groups of employees). Thus, the responses that scored below the overall mean were grouped into a dissatisfied category, while reactions that scored above the overall mean were grouped into a satisfied category. The findings in Table 5 revealed that 44(19.13%) health workers are satisfied with their jobs, while 186 (80.87%) are dissatisfied with their jobs at Dodoma City.

Table 5. Distribution of job satisfaction level

Category	Frequency	Percentage	Overall mean	Standard deviation
			2.90	0.81
Satisfied	44	19.13		
Dissatisfied	186	80.87		

Therefore, the findings suggest that human resources for health working with Local Government Authorities in Dodoma City are experiencing high dissatisfaction with their work. The high level of dissatisfaction sprang from an unsatisfactory salary, lack of recognition efforts, fewer opportunities for growth, and poor supervision from the management. Failure to pay attention to these can negatively affect a company because the employees lack motivation, perform poorly, and have negative attitudes. These symptoms have a way of spreading to other employees, infecting entire departments and the whole company. These results are higher than those conducted in Ethiopia regarding factors for job satisfaction among human resources for health, which revealed that the job satisfaction level was 41.1% while the dissatisfaction level was 58.9% (Abate & Mekonnen, 2021). Also, a study conducted in Zambia and Uganda revealed that 52.3% of respondents were satisfied with their jobs, while 47.7% were dissatisfied (Kim et al., 2021). All these results and experiences are drawn from studies conducted in different countries, but yielding almost the same results implies that job satisfaction is still a major challenge that needs immediate attention to address issues to improve employee satisfaction levels in most African countries.

Association between working conditions and job satisfaction

Further analysis was performed to predict the factors associated with job satisfaction based on the Chi-square test. The findings in Table 6 show that job satisfaction is statistically significantly related to the type of health facility where an employee works ($p=0.0173$) and working conditions ($p<.0001$). The findings show that satisfied health workers from health centres (25.37%) followed by dispensaries (11.54%). Similarly, the findings show that a large proportion of human resources for health are satisfied with improved working conditions (34.18%).

Table 6. Association between working conditions and job satisfaction

Variable	Dissatisfied	Satisfied	Chi-square	P-Value
Type of health facility			8.1162	0.0173
District Hospital	63(90.00)	7(10.00)		
Health Centre	100(74.63)	34(25.37)		
Dispensary	23(88.46)	3(11.54)		
Occupation			4.7447	0.6911
Medical Doctor	9(64.29)	5(35.71)		
Clinical officer	31(83.78)	6(16.22)		
Nurse	46(77.97)	13(22.03)		
Pharmacist	17(89.47)	2(10.53)		
Medical attendant	17(77.27)	5(22.73)		
Laboratory technician	26(83.87)	5(16.13)		
Health officer	14(87.50)	2(12.50)		
Others	26(81.25)	6(18.75)		
Sex			1.0413	0.3075
Male	57(77.03)	17(22.97)		
Female	129(82.69)	27(17.31)		
Age of respondent			2.2810	0.3197

Variable	Dissatisfied	Satisfied	Chi-square	P-Value
20-35	116(78.38)	32(21.62)		
36-50	64(86.49)	10(13.51)		
51 and above	6(75.00)	2(25.00)		
Education qualification			0.2455	0.8845
Secondary	9(81.82)	2(18.18)		
University/college	176(80.73)	42(19.27)		
Other	1(100.00)	0(0.00)		
Working condition			17.6098	<.0001
Poor	134(88.74)	17(11.26)		
Improved	52(65.82)	27(34.18)		

The findings summarised in Table 6 imply that working conditions are significantly associated with job satisfaction. Apart from working conditions, it was also revealed that employee job satisfaction is highly related to the type of health facility an employee works at. The better the working conditions of a health facility, the higher the chance of experiencing job satisfaction. These results conform to the study conducted by Taheri et al. (2020), who concluded that for an organisation to obtain high levels of job satisfaction, better working conditions must be provided to its workforce. Thus, local government authorities need to ensure continuous efforts are directed toward improving the working conditions of employees to achieve high levels of job satisfaction.

The working conditions on job satisfaction among human resource for health

The binary logistic regression model was adopted to assess the influence of the working conditions on job satisfaction. Before deploying the binary logistic regression model, the model fitness was tested using the Omnibus Test of the Model Coefficient. Therefore, as presented in Table 7, the Chi-square of 16.489 and p-value of 0.006 are significant to the log-likelihoods of the model. The findings suggest that there is a model fit in this study. Hence, the variables can be used to predict the results.

Table 7. Omnibus Tests of Model Coefficients

		Chi-square	Sig.
Step 1	Step	16.489	.006
	Block	16.489	.006
	Model	16.489	.006

Then, employing fitted binary logistic regression model to assess variables of working condition and their influence on job satisfaction. Table 8 shows that all the working condition variables assessed were statistically significantly associated with job satisfaction. Specifically, the findings show working tools (p=0.0017), physical working environment (p=0.0071), working hours (p=0.0210), working schedule (p=0.0429), and organisation policies and administration (p=0.0017) were significantly associated with job satisfaction. Thus, as the working conditions improve, the respondents are more likely to have high job satisfaction. Such assertion rhymes with the argument put forward by Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory that improved working conditions result in job

satisfaction of employees in the workplace. This theory urged that better working conditions may not necessarily lead to job satisfaction, but their absence may cause job dissatisfaction. Thus, as the theory puts it, it is very important for an organisation to have improved working conditions favourable to its employees and create a happy workforce.

Table 8. The influence of working conditions on job satisfaction

Indicators	OR [95% CI]	p-value
Working tools	2.435[1.397, 4.245]	0.0017
Physical working environment	1.934[1.196, 3.128]	0.0071
Working hours	1.801[1.093, 2.968]	0.0210
Working schedule	1.782[1.019, 3.118]	0.0429
Organisational policies and administration	2.637[1.440, 4.830]	0.0017

From the findings above, it can be concluded that all variables influence job satisfaction among human resources for health in Local Government Authorities in Dodoma City. That is because, in research, results are considered statistically significant if the p-value is less than 0.05 from which the table above shows that all variables tested provided results that were less than 0.05; hence, they are statistically significant. The findings conform to the study by Lu et al. (2016) in which work schedules influenced job satisfaction while human resources for health were indicated to be influenced by work environment by 56.2%. Also, the findings are supported by Geta et al. (2021), where the work environment indicated a positive and significant association with job satisfaction. Thus, these findings corroborate Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory argument, which emphasises that good working conditions lead to employee job satisfaction. However, the results presented in this study indicated a high level of job dissatisfaction, implying that employees' working conditions are poor. Hence, if the working conditions are poor, the impact is that employees will be demotivated, and others may decide to leave the organisation. To avoid such situations, extra efforts must be put into improving working conditions.

Moreover, the findings by Akinwale and George (2020) support the study findings by drawing on the experience of nurses in government tertiary hospitals in Nigeria, revealing that all predictors of working conditions directly influence the job satisfaction of the nurses. Furthermore, a study by Sirili et al. (2018) shows that low job satisfaction poses challenges to retaining medical doctors in the LGAs in Tanzania. Hence, there is a need to improve the working conditions of employees in all aspects to ensure job satisfaction, retention, commitment, and good performance of human resources for health.

A further step analysis was carried out using unadjusted and adjusted binary logistic regression of working conditions and job satisfaction among human resources for health in Local Government Authorities at Dodoma City. The findings in Table 9 show that, after controlling other variables, only work conditions were statistically significantly associated with job satisfaction ($p=0.0012$). The findings showed that human resource for health with improved working conditions were more likely to report satisfaction with their job (AOR=3.447, $p=0.0006$) compared to workers with poor working conditions.

Table 9: Logistic regression of working conditions on job satisfaction

Variable	UNADJUSTED		ADJUSTED	
	OR [95% CI]	P-Value	AOR [95% CI]	P-Value
Type of health facility				
District Hospital	Ref		Ref	
Health Center	3.060[1.279,7.321]	0.0120	2.185[0.880,5.424]	0.0921
Dispensary	1.174[0.280,4.926]	0.8266	1.013[0.234,4.389]	0.9858
Working condition				
Poor	Ref		Ref	
Improved	4.093[2.061,8.128]	<.0001	3.447[1.699,6.994]	0.0006

The study findings are similar to the study conducted by Raziq and Maulabakhsha (2015) which revealed that working conditions have a positive impact on job satisfaction among workplaces. Thus, management should strive to realise the importance of positive working conditions to maximise employees' job satisfaction. Similarly, Nurvitasari (2019) revealed that working conditions and co-working were positively correlated with job satisfaction. These findings suggest that employees are influenced to like their jobs more if the working conditions are good, attractive, and comfortable. The most important issue for the LGAs is ensuring they take initiative. LGAs should also find donors interested in improving health service provisions and put more effort into improving the working conditions of the people responsible for health service provision. The more improved the working conditions are, the higher the job satisfaction.

Conclusion

Employees working in LGAs at Dodoma City reported extremely low job satisfaction rates (19.13%) compared to 80.87% of dissatisfied workers. The overall level of job satisfaction was measured using the overall mean score (2.9) computed from seven aspects that measured job satisfaction. Findings denoted that from seven aspects, only two aspects were above the overall mean score. In that regard, job security (2.90) and opportunity for growth (3.24) were equal to or greater than the overall mean score. In the same context, salary (2.72), recognition for contribution (2.83), achievement (2.81), supervision (2.88), and job content (2.77) were below the overall mean score. Therefore, the findings concluded that human resources for health working with Local Government Authorities in Dodoma City are experiencing high dissatisfaction with their job. Also, the study concludes that working tools, the working environment, working hours, work schedules, policy and administration are significantly associated with job satisfaction among human health resources in LGAs in Dodoma City. It was also revealed that work conditions were statistically significantly associated with job satisfaction ($p=0.0012$). The findings showed that human resource for health with improved working conditions were more likely to report satisfaction with their job ($AOR=3.447$, $p=0.0006$) compared to workers with poor working conditions. The findings suggest that human resources for health workers working under improved conditions in LGAs experience high job satisfaction compared to those working under unimproved conditions. Thus, the chance of securing a satisfied workforce is guaranteed when working conditions are improved. The study recommends the review of the salary structure of employees considering the current costs of living, the working environment of employees, and the capacity to pay to

improve employees' salaries. Similarly, strategies to recognise efforts should be established, opportunities for employees to advance and grow should be given, and proper and supportive supervision for employees. Not only that but also employees' job content should be related to their skills and knowledge to enhance their ability to perform duties within their capabilities. To continue improving job satisfaction, the government and LGAs should strive to ensure that the working conditions of employees are enhanced through the provision of modern working tools, supply of more human resources for health to help balance working hours and working schedules as well as improving the physical working environment through building more facilities, ensuring safe working environment to accommodate both health employees and the public they serve and designing policies that are favourable to the employees and management.

This study is extremely significant as it helped pinpoint the job satisfaction level of human resources for health in LGAs in Dodoma City. The study also has identified areas where human resources for health are most dissatisfied. This identification could help the LGAs take initiatives in the areas with weaknesses to raise the employees' job satisfaction. Furthermore, this study brings attention to government, policymakers, and other stakeholders regarding how to design strategies and policies that reflect what could be done to improve the situation. However, this study has limitations as local government authorities conducted it in Dodoma City, where the situation from other councils may not be similar; hence, the results cannot be generalised. Furthermore, this study only focused on human resources for health in Local Government Authorities in Dodoma City, but the council has employees working in different sectors such as water, education, agriculture, and administration. A further study on employees' job satisfaction in the other sector may be conducted to make a more comprehensive analysis. Again, the study focused on human resources for health in general, but a human resource for health are categorised into different cadres of specialisation, such as medical doctors, nurses, pharmacists, and laboratory technicians, in which factors for their satisfaction may differ from one cadre to another. Hence, a study on the specific cadre of specialisation in health can be conducted to allow the policy and decision-makers to design separate strategies for improving job satisfaction.

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